

The Use of Deep Geological Repositories to Store High-Level Nuclear Waste in the U.S.: A Brief Review

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I. INTRODUCTION

Since “dry cask” storage was introduced in 1986, there have been no major leaks of high-level nuclear waste from said casks. However, this will not be the case in a few decades, as it is only meant to last in the short term, and the casks must be replaced regularly due to weathering and degradation.^[1] High-level nuclear waste, which makes up about 3% of the total nuclear waste in the United States, primarily consists of spent nuclear fuel.^[2] The fuel is in the form of solid pellets, and these pellets are loaded into tubes, technically called fuel rods, then assembled into bundles, which, during use, are loaded into the reactor core to generate heat.^[3] The spent fuel is first moved into a pool full of water approximately 20 meters. This will absorb the heat and intense radiation so that the fuel can cool down. Once the fuel has cooled down in the spent fuel pool for about 5-7 years, it will be moved into dry cask storage. The cask is lowered into the spent fuel pool, and the fuel bundles are loaded in. Then the cask is sealed while underwater, lifted from the pool, rinsed, and dried, before being moved to a concrete pad on or off site.^[1]

Deep geological repositories are a proposed method for the long-term storage of high-level nuclear waste. In contrast to dry cask storage, which as previously mentioned is meant for short-term storage, deep geological repositories are meant to last for millennia. Deep geological repositories are deep tunnels, typically 200-1000 meters underground, which are filled with capsules similar to the previously mentioned casks and then backfilled with rock or special clay.^[4] The United

III. MAIN

It is recommended that high-level nuclear waste in the United States be stored in deep geological repositories to prevent the spread of radioactive contamination. Gregory J. McCarthy, a professor at the North Dakota State University, states that the

States attempted to build a deep geological repository at Yucca Mountain, NV in the early 1980s. This, however, did not work due to strong political opposition from the state of Nevada.^[5] Strong political opposition to nuclear energy in general, mainly due to the fear of another incident like Chernobyl, Fukushima, or Three Mile Island. This anti-nuclear sentiment has been very common in the last few decades. It is recommended that high-level nuclear waste in the United States be stored in deep geological repositories to prevent the spread of radioactive contamination, ensure the security of said waste, and stabilize the waste from being impacted by large geological events.

II. METHODOLOGY

Studies with a recent date were specifically searched for, as they provide more relevant data. The Eastern Michigan University library database was accessed to acquire most of the articles and studies listed, as well as other well known databases such as ResearchGate, etc... Studies and findings from government agencies were preferred, as they appeared to be much less speculative. Only peer reviewed journal articles were selected. Many different types of studies were included from many different countries and authors so as to be inclusive, and to assist with the inclusion of a diversity of ideas. Studies and articles from well known professors and authors were selected to ensure accuracy, and all studies were thoroughly screened prior to addition.

“dissolution and transport of radionuclides by groundwater are the main threats to the effective isolation of radioactive wastes by burial in deep geological formations.” He also says that, “Waste-rock interaction under rather moderate temperature-pressure conditions will be rapid and extensive if the container is breached.”^[6] This is concerning due to

uncertainties of the stability of the containers over large time scales, such as tens of thousands of years. The spread of radioactive contamination could mean contaminated groundwater, and therefore drinking water, crops, livestock, and soil in general. Even small amounts of radioactive contamination can bioaccumulate and increase concentration to harmful levels over time.^[7] A notable example of a possibly favorable outcome after the release of radioactive contamination is the formation of Na-pollucite (a naturally occurring mineral), which is formed under conditions found in deep geological formations, capable of including radioactive ¹³⁷Cs (among other radionuclides), a fission product, into its structure.^[6] Another notable example of an isolation method is the employment of so-called bioremediation. This is where microorganisms can reduce uranium 6+, U(VI), in the uranyl ion ([UO₂]²⁺), which is highly water soluble, to uranium 4+, U(IV), almost completely insoluble in water. They can also chemically bind to the radionuclide of interest (usually uranium) to significantly decrease mobility. The process of reduction from U(VI) to U(IV) is the most studied of the two. Not only can this process drastically reduce mobility, but it can also lower toxicity of the uranium itself.^[8] Stephan Hilpmann, a PostDoc at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf Dresden, claims that microbial uranium bioremediation “offers several advantages over conventional remediation methods. These include its potential for in-situ application, minimal environmental disturbance, absence of secondary pollution, and relatively low cost.” Another interesting form of isolation is the use of vitrification. This technique of vitrification has been implemented since the mid 1960s. Vitrification is the process of adding high level waste (usually in powder form) to a, usually borosilicate, glass base, and then melting it at very high temperatures to fuse the radioactive waste and trap it inside of the glass matrix. This prevents most leakage of the radionuclides.^[9] Vitrification does however have some downsides, such as the volatilization of technetium (^{99g}Tc), which would result in losses in the nuclear waste, recycling issues, and higher cost.^[10]

Additionally, it is recommended that high-level nuclear waste in the United States be stored in deep geological repositories to ensure the security of said waste. The security of high-level nuclear waste is important to ensure long-term stability of the waste. Future human activity may pose significant risk to the long-term security of deep geological repositories. Terry L. Tolan, a researcher at the Portland State University, says that examples of potentially disruptive human activities may include “drilling, mining, archaeological exhumation, development of injection wells, waste recovery, weapons testing, and war.”^[15] Heejae Ju concluded that recovering radioactive waste from a repository “was estimated to take

2–18 months.”^[14] This is not very long, especially if related technology advances. One method which has been proposed for the long-term security of deep geological repository sites once shut down is the use of markers which contain either subliminal messaging, large threatening objects, or regular warning signs. One example of a proposed marker design is the “black hole.” This would be a large flat area made entirely from black concrete or granite, which is intended to become extremely hot under the sun. This would make the region effectively uninhabitable. Other proposed markers consist of large spikes sticking out of the ground or large “forbidding blocks” around the perimeter of the site. As for actual written signs, a few “levels” of message have been proposed. An example of this is a proposed sign which roughly reads “This place is a message ... Sending this message was important to us. We considered ourselves to be a powerful culture. This place is not a place of honor ... no highly esteemed deed is commemorated here... nothing valued is here.” These all attempt to use words and symbols which can still be easily recognized as harmful, or negative, even thousands of years in the future.^[11] It has also been recommended “marking the site with large earthen berms.” These berms would be in the shape of the classic trefoil design to indicate radioactive contamination.^[12] Waste may want to be accessed intentionally or on accident to recover nuclear materials, attempt to mine in the area, or attempt to recover other precious materials from the site. This technology was developed for the WIPP (Waste Isolation Pilot Plant) in New Mexico, which serves as a disposal site for high-level radioactive waste in the United States.^[11]

Lastly, it is recommended that high-level nuclear waste in the United States be stored in deep geological repositories to stabilize the waste from large geological events. Such events could potentially damage the buried casks in which the waste is stored, and lead to the previously mentioned contamination. Earthquakes will be taken as an example for a major geological event. F.M. McEvoy, who does geological survey work, states that earthquakes, which are the result of instantaneous geological fault movements, “may give rise to vibratory hazard where possible strong shaking may, depending on the ... concept and design, cause damage.”^[16] The National Cooperative for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste (NAGRA) in their paper “Earthquakes. No Danger to Deep Storage Facilities” also states that underground structures “are less at risk during an earthquake than buildings on the Earth's surface.”^[13] This implies that if there is no large fault at the location of burial, then the chances of an earthquake, or for that matter any other large geological event, is very unlikely to occur. It is also very unlikely that such an event would cause any significant damage to the buried casks.

It is recommended to store waste in an area which is geologically inactive, however future activity may not prove disastrous.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, deep geological repositories are one of the safest ways that we currently have to store high-level nuclear waste in the long term to prevent radioactive contamination, ensure the security of the waste, and stabilize the waste from large geological events.

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